

Manufacture of Products, and Consumer's Rights

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Abstract:

Consumer's rights plays important role, and since we all are consumers, producers too does consumes, making them consumers, needing consumer's rights. Similarly, manufacturing of any product from any given product is what our industries, Market, and livelihood depends. In this article, we have attempted to describe about consumers rights, by means of identification provided for each goods, relying on identification to provide basic knowledge about consumers about contents or ingredients in products.

Keywords: Consumers's Rights, Ingredients, Consituted things, Products, Goods, Arjun Dahal, arjundahalard

Introduction:

Even the soldiers who talke oath to die for nation, or any fellow taking oath, swore before sitting in any chair, wouldn't like to die, due to foods, or contents in food. Thus we won't discuss about Consumer's rights, to relate it with health, hygeine, and proper functioning of our body, which if talked for each cell of our body, discussing as multicellular organism might form legthy epic. Thus, we shall leave such topics to generous readers, who might persue to make epic, by studying each complement, for sake of humanity, and being lazy shall proceed towards brief discussion as per title of our manuscript.

Manufacture of Products:

We shall discuss about products, and when any product is prepared, to make it available in market, then, by virtue of money, revenues and taxtion are discussed, which too are essential parts to sustain government, depending upon work, allowing to analyse the utilty of revenues and taxation. In products, we mostly find stickers, or even labels where lot of topics are written. Even the medicine, that we do eat

while we are ill, contains constituents, which is hard for us to understand, but are understood by fellows with expertise in chemical analysis and components.

Health Care:

Since we all aren't doctors, and we don't know about our body much, we can rely on the products, depending upon the compositions and constituents. Proteins, Calciums, Irons are essential, and are available to without prescription of doctors, pharmacists or chemists. It is true that, excess of much items would result disorder. And we can take care of our health care by observing the constituents, though we feel lazy.

About Products:

Products and Market Value, are important topics, and we shall begin with an example of application letter, which I had sent to Inland Revenue Department, for making revenue stickers more scientific.

When that is generalized, then, not only the product information can be made available, but can even be discussed to make more systematic. GPS can be added to track location, so that, from manufacturer, till retailer, goods can be precisely traced. Use of GPS, would only aid, to study supply and demand, time interval, and quality of goods, when arrived and received, by any entity, after manufacturer sells it, or send it in market.

Importance of Revenue Sticker, or any sticker, has importance, due to national laws. That would mean, any manufacturer by means of revenue sticker is safe only from revenue and taxation, but not from constituents, in any products, and that is why, constituents are necessary, to let peoples know.

Intelligences, Conspiracy Theories, and Artificial Intelligences:

Components like as chips that are available in nature which after manufacturing becomes products, and that we do use, in our gadgets to talk about progress in technology, too are products of nature, based manufacturing.

That means, we can be bioticrobot or an bioandroid. A common example is our cellphones and apps, that do claim to have discuss about health and habits when are used as per our daily data, then that would be doing like as computer simulation, to study about our body.

Then comes topics of gadgets, which are hard to discuss, because of the vast difference created by nature, in natural products. We can argue all natural products are natural, thus all might has common element, to understand; which; then would lead us to study of fairy tales, where humans does speaks to

animals, plants, trees, or even bacteria, viruses, fungus, rocks, mountains, and would be like as cartoon kingdom, that we generally see in cartoon.

When we do consider about living beings and non-living beings, then it discussion would be like as of wheelchair, and computer, of great scientist Stephan Hawkings, that, as per news sources would rely on his cheeks, for communication, quite similiar to that of Galvani's twiching of muscle in frog, and I am not aware of such gadgets, but that too was as per news source.

Even if we would apply such gadgets to ourselves, then, we mightn't have wheelchair, but some parts, controlled by gadgets, where gadgets does lies with us.

When topics of will is discussed, then that would be same like as stories of religion, where Gods would fly in air, but different then that of cartoon. That would be same like as Jesus came from sky, or pleading to Jesus, to come from sky again.

That is same for all stories of religion, not only of Biblical, as in Vedic stories, Sages have been talked, to have flewn in air, as well as creating and destroying, doing unbelievable things, due to their power attained from meditation, and education.

Few Questions Answered:

I was questioned by a lady fellow, who talked herself as lady fellow at Embassy of U.S.A, Maharajgunj, Nepal, and her question was how to make an agent.

That might be unbeautiful question, but without a doubt, Intelligences too would argue about goodness, and righteousness. And more then Movie Hitman: Agent 47, we all can be agents, allowing either other fellows or, ourselves, controlling us, relying on education.

Either fellows would be Marvel Character, like as Spiderman, Superman, Batman, Hulk, or sage, or even Jesus, who could came from sky, and were different then of versions of movies.

For an example, if I would insert some chips, allowing to observe chemical components, like as for acid, base, and salt, along with ph-value, and study same like as by means of phenolpthalin, Blue Litmus, Red Limus, or Universal Indicator, then that would provide us knowledge about neutralization reaction, where acid and base yields salt and water. Water is liquid, where as salt is taste.

Our mind prefers tasty things, thus besides consumer's rights, we have to take care of our health as well, and even that acid base reaction would be dangerous to our body, as our body has Hydrochloric acid in tiny amount.

Similiar ways can be studied to make body powerful, as well as training mind, where as agent formed as a product, would rely on for which purpose, would the agent be used.

Actknowledgements:

My actknowledgements to the application letter subnitted to Inland Reveneue Department and other deparment of Nepal, as well as fellows, who relied in discussion of militery, intelligences, militery intelligences, agents, power, weapons, warfare, to argue about peace, security and defense.